

Monastery of Panagia (Virgin) Chozoviotissa

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Entry tags: Amorgos island, Amorgos island, Christian, Religious Group, Christian Orthodox, Greek, Aegean, Language, Religious Place, Orthodoxy

The Monastery of Panagia (Virgin) Chozoviotissa on the south of Amorgos sits on the side of a cliff overlooking the Aegean Sea, 2 km away from the Chora, the main settlement of the island. It operates as a male Monastery and officially celebrates the feast of the Entrance of the Virgin Mary to the Temple (Eisodia tis Theotokou in Greek) on November 21. The Monastery's name comes from the corruption of "Hozivitissa" or "Kozovitissa", which in turn is a corruption of the toponym "Hozeva" or "Koziva" in the Holy Land (present day Wadi Qilt, Jericho, Palestine), where important Orthodox Monasteries have existed since the early Christian period. According to local/oral tradition, the icon of Panagia Chozoviotissa arrived during the period of Iconoclasm by the sea at the bay of saint Anna, located near the place where the Monastery was built. The correlation of the oral tradition with the information provided by the Byzantine chroniclers, mainly Theophanes, historical events, as well as later written evidence handed down by manuscripts and the Patriarchal sigillia of the Monastery, allow to date the initial building core to the second half of the 9th century, so in the years that have followed the discovery of the icon of the Virgin. The emperor Alexios I Komnenos has restored the Monastery in 1088, which was also conferred the right of stauropegion, i.e. to be self-governed and independent from local ecclesiastical hierarchy. During the Venetian occupation of the island (1296-1537) significant changes and expansions were made to the initial building. The Monastery continued to prosper during the Ottoman period (1537-1824). Throughout its long history it was granted lands on the islands of Crete, Leros, Naxos, Paros, Astypalaia, Ios as well as hermitages in Keros, Nikouria, and Grambussa. The complex which has eight floors is 40m long, while its width does not exceed 5m. The floors are connected by narrow stone staircases, built or carved into the rock. The labyrinthic interior of the structure is characterized by the many arches (byzantine, gothic etc.) and frames built by different materials. The cells of the monks, the refectory, the kitchen, the warehouses, the cisterns, the wells etc. were carved into the rock. In the small vaulted church (katholikon) of the Monastery can be found the two icons of the Virgin Chozoviotissa, and the chisel of the builder through which he was indicated the place where the Virgin wanted the Monastery to be constructed. Another important relic related to the history of the Monastery is the silver hexapterygon (ceremonial fan used in Eastern Christian worship) which has an inscription indicating that the Monastery was restored by emperor Alexios I Komnenos. The space behind the entrance of the Monastery currently houses an exhibition of relics and artefacts such as liturgical vessels, reliquaries, inscriptions, manuscripts, liturgical vestments, icons, wooden carvings and Early modern books.

Date Range: 850 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Aegean Sea, Greece, Amorgos island

Region tags: Greece, Aegean, Amorgos island

The Monastery of Panagia Chozoviotissa on the
Monastery of Amorgos, Aegean island, Greece

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Maragkou, L. Η Μονή Της Παναγίας Της Χοζοβιώτισσας Στην Αμοργό. Athens, 1999.
- Source 2: Lamprinides, M. Χοζοβιώτισσα. Η Χιλιόχρονη Μονή Της Αμοργού. Athens, 1979.
- Source 3: Dikaios, A. “Μονή Παναγίας Χοζοβιώτισσας Αμοργού,” In Παναγία Εκατονταπυλιανή Πάρου και Χοζοβιώτισσα Αμοργού. Athens, n.d.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: http://odysseus.culture.gr/h/2/gh251.jsp?obj_id=1564
- Source 1 Description: Monastery of Panagia Chozoviotissa, Ministry of Culture and Sports of Greece
- Source 2 URL: <https://youtu.be/657k8lpfo64>
- Source 2 Description: Documentary about the Monastery of Panagia Chozoviotissa

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

- No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Other [specify]: The Monastery sits on the side of a cliff overlooking the Aegean Sea

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

- Yes

Type of feature

- Leveling of ground
- Terracing
- Water feature

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

- No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– No

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– Yes

↳ Is there an established route of travel connecting it to a wider transportation network:

– Yes

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

–Other [specify]: The Monastery which was built on the site of a cliff has eight floors, which measure 40m long, while its width does not exceed 5m

↳ One single feature

–Other [specify]: A single structure with many various features carved into the rock

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: The Monastery was founded in the 9th century, renovated in 1088, while it was also restored later as well

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

–Other [specify]: The Monastery was built for worship but also for hosting a monastic community

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: However, the monastic community is ceaselessly praying to God, the Virgin and various saints.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Notes: It was not founded by an official political entity. However, it was restored in 1088 by the Byzantine emperor Alexios I Komnenos

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– No

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Yes

↳ Specify

–Other [specify]: The Monastery was built where the icon of the Virgin Chozoviotissa was found

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

↳ Specify

–Other [specify]: The Monastery was built where the icon of the Virgin Chozoviotissa was found

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

–Other [specify]: The Monastery was built where the icon of the Virgin Chozoviotissa was found

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– Yes

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Wood
– Yes

↳ Grass
– Yes

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: Marble

– Yes

↳ Earth
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Sand
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– Yes

↳ Clay
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Marble

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– No

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: Panel paintings (icons)

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The Son of God, Jesus Christ

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Saints, the Mother of God, Angels

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Christ, Virgin Mary and the Saints are depicted

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: They are included in the narrative scenes

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Notes: Inscriptions always accompany Orthodox figural iconography and portraits

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Aniconic decoration exclusively

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

Notes: Icons

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

Notes: The katholikon of the Monastery is not decorated with frescoes. There are however small compositions at different areas of the monastic complex

↳ Type

–'True' fresco

–Secco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: The remains of the monks of the Monastery are kept in the ossuary

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Notes: The monks and pilgrims are though praying at the Monastery

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: However, pilgrims come to pray and worship the icon of the Virgin Chozoviotissa

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: The feast of the Monastery on November 21 is a large-scale ritual in which are involved the habitants of the island of Amorgos and many other visitors/pilgrims

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Every day the Divine liturgy is celebrated

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: Unknown

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Every day but mainly every Sunday

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

Notes: The monks are following the Orthodox rite

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

Notes: The monks are following the Orthodox rite

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

Notes: Pilgrims or any visitor can offer anything he/she wishes

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Notes: Material offerings can be valuable objects or things that are not at all costly. What matters is the offering and not the value

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Notes: Material offerings can be anything

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Material offerings can be anything and everything including money, objects, lands etc.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Notes: Attendance to worship is not mandatory for the pilgrims. It is though for the monks living there

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: The Monastery was reconstructed in 1088. Several other reparations took also place

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

Notes: The monks living at the Monastery

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: The place is maintained also by the Ministry of Culture

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:
– optional (common)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:
– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:
– No

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):
– Yes

↳ Are these routes maintained together with the place:
– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned

with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: Male

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

Notes: Every monastic community is led by the abbot superior

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: Panagia Chozoviotissa is a functioning male Monastery

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The Ministry of Culture and Sports of Greece, as well the Church of Greece are responsible for the maintenance and preservation of the Monastery

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– I don't know

Notes: It is possible since the Monastery owns lands on different Greek islands

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– I don't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Notes: Archives

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Monastery of Panagia (Virgin) Chozoviotissa, Maragkou, L.. Η Μονή Της Παναγίας Της Χοζοβιώτισσας Στην Αμοργό. Athens, 1999.

Reference: Monastery of Panagia (Virgin) Chozoviotissa, Lamprinides, M.. Χοζοβιώτισσα. Η Χιλιόχρονη Μονή Της Αμοργού. Athens, 1979.

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Reference: Monastery of Panagia (Virgin) Chozoviotissa, Simos, E.. “Παναγία Χοζοβιώτισσα, Η Μονή Της Αμοργού”, Έξοδος στην κοινωνία και τη ζωή, 14 (1995).